

Gate-Controlled Photoresponse in an Individual Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Modified with a Fluorescent Protein

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Bionanohybrids of carbon nanotubes and fluorescent proteins (FPs) are a promising class of materials for optoelectronic applications. Understanding and controlling the charge transport mechanism between FPs and carbon nanotubes are critical to achieving functional reproducibility and exploring novel synergetic effects. This work demonstrates a novel phenomenon of photocurrent generation in field-effect transistors based on the conjugation of an individual single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) and FPs. When studying the effect of gate voltage on the photoresponse, reversible switching from fast positive to a slow negative photoresponse in bionanohybrids associated with depletion and accumulation modes, respectively is observed. The latter demonstrates a stable memory effect after the light is turned off. It is revealed that in depletion mode, the charge carriers from the protein are not trapped at the interface due to effective screening by the gate potential. It is suggested that the main mechanism in photoresponse switching is a competitive effect between photogating and effective photodoping of the SWCNT by charges trapped at the nanotube interface. The noticeable effect of water molecules can support proton transfer as the main mechanism of charge transfer. This result illustrates that SWCNT/FP bionanohybrids bear great potential for the realization of novel optoelectronic devices.

1. Introduction

Currently, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are proposed as a promising material for circuit-level photonic synapse development as a building block of neuromorphic optoelectronic computing. Different methods, mainly based on nanohybrids of CNTs and photosensitive nanostructures, have been applied to increase the photosensitivity of CNT-based optoelectronic devices. Nanohybrids of nanotubes with perovskite quantum dots,^[1] inorganic semiconducting quantum dots,^[2] and gold nanoparticles^[3] are efficient ways to make highly sensitive optoelectronic sensors. Recently, it was demonstrated that CNT-based hybrids with photosensitive biomolecules are a promising approach to provide effective exciton dissociation in high-performance CNT-based photodetectors.^[4]

Fluorescent proteins (FPs) offer unique properties of light conversion

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Figure 1. The immobilization of mKate2 on individual SWCNT FET: a) Optical image of the electrodes contacting SWCNTs (inset: AFM image of an individual SWCNT). b) Schematic illustration of the SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET after assembling. c) Raman shifts for SWCNT before and after immobilization of mKate2. I_D versus V_{DS} d) and I_D versus V_G e) curves were measured after each assembly step.

with almost 100% efficiency of the chromophore and high stability due to the protein's barrel-shaped tertiary structure. A unique combination of high quantum yield, wavelength selectivity, and stability of chromophore in proteins, along with the unique electronic and optical properties of nanotubes, provides high sensitivity and flexibility in device operation. FPs are now being actively studied for applications in optoelectronics and photovoltaics.^[5,6] Previously, we demonstrated that the green FP can alter the optoelectronic properties of semiconducting single-walled CNT (sc-SWCNT) depending on specific binding sites, opening a prospective way for optically driven current modulators and optoelectronic memory devices.^[7] However, the mechanism of the coupling between FP and nanotubes has not been yet properly investigated.^[8] At the same time, an in-depth understanding of this mechanism might serve not only fundamental aspects but also facilitate the development of optically controlled reliable bio-nanohybrid devices.

In this work, we examine the mechanism of charge transfer between red FP mKate2 and individual SWCNTs under light illumination in the configuration of a field-effect transistor (FET) with a bottom gate. We demonstrate that by varying the gate voltage applied to the SWCNT channel, one can switch between positive and negative photoresponses. The positive one is due to the photogating effect in the SWCNT, and the negative photoresponse is likely due to both electron transport from the chromophore and positive charges trapped at the interface in close vicinity to

the nanotube. While the photogating effect is broadband and demonstrates fast optical switching, the negative photoresponse demonstrates the phenomenon of optoelectronic memory and is selective to the wavelength corresponding to the absorption of mKate2.

2. Results and Discussion

Optical and atomic force microscopy (AFM) images, as well as the design and fabrication scheme of a FET based on SWCNT modified with a fluorescent protein, are shown in **Figures 1a,b** and **S1** (Supporting Information). Two Pd/Cr electrodes cover a SWCNT with a length of 12 μm and a diameter of ca. 1.5 nm. The red fluorescent protein (mKate2) was selected for its uniform distribution of lysine residues protruding to the outside on the molecule's surface, which ensures N-Hydroxysuccinimide (NHS)-NH₂-based immobilization on the nanotubes with random protein orientation (see *Experimental section*). Before and after FP immobilization, we carried out AFM, Raman, and electrical characterization. After binding mKate2, the nanotube/FP conjugate height increased ≈ 3.5 nm (Figure **S2**, Supporting Information) in accordance with average size of FPs.^[8] We observed a very dense population of mKate2 on the surface of the nanotube with an average distribution of one protein per 35 ± 5 nm (Figure **S2f**, Supporting Information). The population density of proteins depends on the number of binding sites on FP close to

Figure 2. The photoresponse in SWCNT FET. Photoresponse at 590 nm (blue) and 390 nm (cyan) wavelengths of pristine SWCNT a) and modified with PBASE/mKate2 b), where arrows show LED On and Off time. c) Photocurrent in SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 at different power of 390 nm irradiation. Grey dashed lines show LED On and Off time. d) Dependence of saturated photocurrent on the irradiation power of the 390 nm LED.

the nanotube rather than concentration in solution.^[7,8] As far as lysine moieties are randomly distributed over the FP surface the binding density is high, but still can be limited by the density of adsorbed 1-Pyrenebutyric acid NHS ester (PBASE) molecules. We didn't observe photoluminescence (PL) from individual nanotubes decorated with FPs due to quenching by the substrate (Figure S3a, Supporting Information). Raman curves demonstrate weak doping of nanotubes with a slight redshift of the G mode (from 1600.4 to 1599.5 cm^{-1}) after PBASE deposition and a blueshift (to 1601.3 cm^{-1}) when the protein binds (Figure 1c). It should be stated that the apparent absence of a D mode (≈ 1350 cm^{-1}) proves the high quality of the prepared nanotubes. Initial G band position can be shifted due to doping^[9] by adsorbed molecules from the environment or residuals left after the photolithography process. However, similar to the previous results by other groups,^[8] no organic optical bands appear because of protein the low-density packaging. The annealing process of the nanotube during SWCNT FET manufacturing (see *Experimental section*) lowered the Schottky barrier in the SWCNT/Pd interface, which increased the conductivity of the FET channel to ≈ 2 μS (Figure 1d). A noticeable decrease in drain current I_D after PBASE deposition relates to the increased number of scattering centers in the nanotube, as well as doping from the adsorbed aromatic rings. In general, conductivity decreases after each step of protein immobilization due to the decrease in charge carriers' mobility and partial doping of nanotubes. In this work, we selected only FETs whose channels demonstrate non-zero conductivity in the Off state, which can be related to either quasi-metallic or small band gap semiconducting nanotubes, or small bundles

containing both types. Moreover, the supporting substrate can greatly influence the band gap of the nanotubes.^[10] Initial dependence of I_D versus gate voltage V_G demonstrates a change in current by more than an order of magnitude, and the minimal current in the depletion mode saturates at ≈ 70 nA at the charge neutrality point ($V_{DS} = 100$ mV) (Figure 1e). When the SWCNT FET is functionalized with FPs and measured in the dark, the drain current decreases. We observed a shift of threshold gate voltage to more positive values after PBASE functionalization (Figure S4, Supporting Information). PBASE is attaching to the surface of the SWCNTs via π - π interaction with additional *p*-doping of nanotube.^[11] After mKate2 immobilization the left shift of the I_D - V_{GS} curves are typical for n-type doping,^[12] which could be due to either direct electron transfer from the protein^[13] or electrostatic doping caused by positive charges on the surface of the protein^[14] under normal conditions. There is always an inevitable conductive level in the selected SWCNT FETs at room temperature. The hysteresis of the transfer characteristic can be attributed to the charge traps in silicon oxide, oxygen, or water molecules close to the carbon nanotubes.^[15] PBASE forms a quasi-second layer shell on the nanotube surface, resulting in an increased band gap and a lowering of minimal current.^[16]

We investigated the photoresponse of pristine and FP-modified SWCNT FETs under 590 and 390 nm irradiation wavelengths (mKate2 main absorption bands,^[17] see Figure S3b, Supporting Information). For the pristine SWCNT, we observed a positive photoresponse (current increase) (Figure 2a) related to the photogating effect^[18,19] due to charge accumulation at the interface of silicon and silicon oxide.^[20] Also, the metal oxide

interfaces between the nanotube and electrode can provide a positive photoresponse under light illumination.^[21] The response is relatively fast, with a time constant $\tau < 1$ s, which is limited by the capacity of the electrodes and the long nanotube channel and does not depend on the illumination wavelength.^[22] It is known that the photogating effect is observed in CNT-based FETs only for lightly n-doped Si substrates.^[23] In our experiments, we initially had a highly doped silicon substrate, but due to thermal annealing (see *Experimental section*), we assume the diffusion of boron ions in the Si substrate.

For SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET, a similar positive response is preserved for wavelengths outside the absorption range of the protein (Figure S5, Supporting Information). The conjugation of SWCNTs and FPs can result in both reduced fluorescence intensity and prolonged photobleaching lifetime.^[8] Considering that native mKate2 exhibits at least two excitation bands,^[17] we can assume the presence of a specific photoresponse in SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET for both wavelengths. The photoresponse upon 590 and 390 nm illumination (Figure 2b) was negative (decrease in conductivity), which can be caused by electron transfer from proteins to the nanotube and decreasing the concentration of main charge carriers in the valence band, as discussed in our previous work.^[7] For FPs, a hopping mechanism of electron transfer in an excited state has been described previously;^[24] tunneling is a less probable process in such systems. Hopping via aromatic residues has also been confirmed experimentally in hybrid protein-semiconductor systems.^[13] Thus, we assume the hopping mechanism is more likely since it was reliably found in homologous proteins. Based on FPs distribution density one can calculate that for the channel of 10 μm length ≈ 300 proteins can be immobilized. Therefore, the specific orientation of each individual protein will not affect the device's performance. For the number of devices created, we observed similar behavior both in change of transfer characteristics (Figure S4, Supporting Information) and in photoresponse (Figure S6, Supporting Information) as well as reproducibility.

The response time is much longer ($\tau_1 = 670$ s) and there is a long-term memory effect after the light is turned off, likely due to charged deeper traps^[11] at the interface of SWCNT and FPs. The photoresponse depends on illumination power and can be observed for LED power above 5 mW (Figure 2c). Moreover, the current-power dependence has a saturation maximum (Figure 2d) for LED power above 20 mW. The photoresponse is less pronounced for 590 nm (Figure S7a, Supporting Information). We observed that for the pristine SWCNT/PBASE FET the photocurrent is slightly increasing with power showing saturation in photogating effect due to limited number of charges at the interface of silicon and its oxide.^[25] After FPs immobilization, the positive photocurrent is decreasing with power due to the absorption of the denatured FP and competitive effect of photogating and charge transfer from FPs.

We noticed that response to 590 nm is weaker than to 390 nm (Figure 2b). There are two possible mechanisms of such behavior. If the response is caused by the native protein, then we can assume that charge transfer proceeds well from the immature fraction of the chromophore (i.e., neutral chromophore of the GFP type with absorption maximum at 390 nm), and from the mature chromophore of the DsRed type (590 nm) charge transfer does not happen. On the contrary, if the response is caused

by a denatured protein, the response can go through aromatic residues or through a chromophore, which is usually preserved during denaturation. The chromophore of a denatured protein can absorb at both 390 and 450 nm depending on the denaturation mechanism. Thus, appearance of the effect upon irradiation at 390 nm can be valid for both states of the protein. Nevertheless, these aromatic groups are unlikely to produce an effective flow of electrons, and the probability of electron transfer will decrease significantly as the distance from the chromophore to the nearest intermediate acceptors (e.g., tyrosine residues) increases upon denaturation. It should be noted that direct observation of absorption bands in FP immobilized on SWCNTs is challenging due to high adsorption of nanotubes (Figure S3c, Supporting Information). However, the increase of light absorption in the range of 300–500 nm for SWCNTs modified with FPs can be related to the deactivation of the red chromophore form when binding FP and nanotube.

The photogating effect in pristine SWCNT depends on the gate voltage and at -15 V, when the nanotube channel is in accumulation mode, it becomes negligible because additional charge carriers cannot be generated (Figure 3a). Thus, the effect is only observed in the linear part of the transfer curve with the highest gain. The right shift of the transfer curves (Figure 3b) confirms the photogating effect via charge accumulation in the substrate interface under light illumination. For SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET, we observed the switching between positive and negative photoresponses for different gate voltages applied (Figure 3c). Though PBASE can transfer additional charges under 390 nm irradiation we observed only increase of photocurrent in SWCNT/PBASE FET mainly due to shift of the threshold voltage (Figure S7b, Supporting Information). Notably, during multiple cycles of light pulses, we observed a memory effect for the negative photoresponse in SWCNT/FPs conjugates. The trapped charges at the interface between the nanotube and FP can be responsible for the memory state without light.^[26]

To understand in-depth the observed phenomena of photoresponse switching, we discuss the charge transfer under light illumination. First, aerosol CVD mainly provides individual SWCNT or small bundles, which can contain both metallic and semiconducting nanotubes. It is obvious that at the charge neutrality point, we have non-zero current due to the small band gap (including metallic) or the presence of nanotubes of both types in a bundle. Moreover, when the nanotube channel is long, the channel is in depletion mode at $V_G = 0$ V due to the presence of trapped states at the nanotube/substrate interface. Only a small current is possible by free charge carriers thermally transferred over the small band gap at room temperature.^[27] In our previous work, for pristine sc-SWCNT bundles, we showed the channel is opened only at negative gate voltages.^[7] Under light irradiation, different photocurrent generation mechanisms dominate in the response of quasi-metallic nanotubes and small band gap semiconducting nanotubes.^[28,29] Though the contact between the nanotube and metal electrodes has Ohmic behavior after annealing, only a small barrier and the difference between source and drain barriers can result in a weak positive photoresponse in the FET. This can lead to the weak photoresponse of the pristine SWCNT shown previously for nanotubes in the same configuration^[30] and photocurrent caused by generated $e-h$ pairs

Figure 3. Photoresponse of pristine SWCNT FET to cyclic on/off light irradiation at different gate voltages a) and transfer curves with and without illumination b). SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET photoresponse to cyclic irradiation by 390 nm at various gate voltages: 0, -5, and -15 V c). d) Transfer curves for mKate2/SWCNT FET with and without 390 nm irradiation (inset: schematics of the photoresponse mechanism in SWCNT/FP FET in depletion and accumulation modes).

in SWCNTs separated by an electric field.^[31] A nanotube with a small bandgap provides very fast charge separation^[29] that can be responsible for the fast photoresponse observed (Figure 3a). We assume the positive fast photoresponse originates from the SWCNTs channel rather than the barrier in the contact area due to interfacial photogating,^[32] and this response does not depend on the wavelength. We observe the right shift of the transfer curves for pristine SWCNTs (Figure 3b). As far as the photogating effect is responsible only for the gate threshold voltage shift, the photoresponse decreases for high negative voltages applied to the silicon substrate.

In the case of SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 conjugate, we have to consider the nanotube/FP hetero-interface effect, which plays a major role in the functionality and performance of such a bio-nanohybrid device.^[33] The observed increase in negative photoresponse at highly negative gate voltages (e.g., $V_G = -15$ V) is due to the charge transfer from the fluorescent protein under light irradiation^[34] (Figure 3c). We propose that this results from the charges trapping at the interfaces of FP and nanotube or FP and substrate in the direct vicinity of the nanotube. Because of their proximity, these trapped charges modulate the nanotube conductance more efficiently than the back gate.^[26] In depletion mode, the charge transfer from mKate2 to traps is effectively screened,^[35] while negative gate voltage holds charges on the traps. Under negative gate voltage, positive charges (either holes or protons via water tunnels in FP^[8,36,37]) can be trapped at the protein and substrate interface. As these charges are in close vicinity to the nanotube, they affect channel conductivity much stronger, resulting in a decrease in conductivity. The process is

limited by the diffusion of protons via water tunnels, resulting in a long response time. We suggest that proton transfer and trapping at the interface to be the main mechanism responsible for the memory effect in SWCNT/FP FETs.

To prove this assumption, we performed measurements in different environments, which may affect proton transport.^[38] The effect of drying SWCNT/mKate2 FET after holding it for 30 min in an Ar atmosphere was investigated. For reactivation of the nanotube/FP interface, we put a water droplet on the device followed by blowing it out before the measurements. We noticed that the photoresponse did not change its mechanism after holding FET in the inert atmosphere and demonstrated a response time constant $\tau_1 = 252$ s (Figure 4a). After water soaking, we observed an increase in negative photocurrent in the channel by about three times and a decrease τ_1 to 181 s. I_D - V_G curves demonstrated the hysteresis widening under illumination with a left shift and a decrease in total conductivity (Figure 4b). While treatment in Ar can remove weakly adsorbed water molecules on the nanotube,^[39] we believe that the water molecules associated with proteins are preserved. Notably, drying and wetting do not affect the fast mechanism of positive photoresponse in the channel of the bio-nanohybrid, which is related to photogating. Environmental change alters the negative photoresponse related to charge transfer from FP to SWCNT initiated by specific wavelength.

The negative photoresponse is much slower compared to photogating and does not affect the transfer curve during light irradiation (Figure 3d). On the contrary, at the initial stage when the light is on, we observed a small right shift of the transfer curve that corresponds to the peak in the time course during the first

Figure 4. Photoresponse in SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 FET after holding in Ar and water. a) Time course of photocurrent under a 390 nm LED pulse after exposure to Ar (blue) and water (cyan), where arrows show LED on and off time. b) I_D - V_G curves measured before (blue) and 1 min after the LED pulse (cyan) for device exposure to Ar (dashed lines) and water (solid lines). The arrow shows the shift of curves after the light pulse.

seconds of the light pulse (Figure 2b). After a certain time (more than a minute), the accumulated positive charges in the vicinity of the nanotube initiate a more effective screening the charges in the silicon substrate, resulting in the left and downward shift of the transfer curves after irradiation (Figure S8, Supporting Information). These results are similar to the accumulation of charge on the traps in the vicinity of the nanotube, covered by a photosensitive semiconducting polymer.^[26] Thus, when light irradiates the SWCNT FET in depletion mode, the electrons generated in the substrate increase the current in the nanotube. At the same time, the trapped charges generated by FP are screened by the charges in the substrate or relaxed quickly due to the absence of gate potential. The negative photoresponse observed in accumulation mode is due to the negative gate voltage holding the positive charges (protons) on deep traps at the interfaces between the nanotube and protein. These traps are responsible for both a longer response time and a decrease in current. Interestingly, the presence of pair pulse facilitation (PPF) property in the response of the device is observed (Figure 3c). Indeed, after the first pulse stimulus, the second pulse with the same power comes after 200 s and enhances the long-term memory.^[1] The second and subsequent light stimuli at negative gate voltages provide more photogenerated positive charges at traps that result in decreased device conductance (Figure 3c). Nevertheless, the photogating process is two orders of magnitude faster than trapping and these traps are released rapidly for depletion mode (at $V_G \geq 0$ V). The “memory state” can be rewritten by applying of fast gate voltage sweep.^[7] In the linear regime of transconductance (e.g., $V_G = -5$ V), both mechanisms are possible at the FP-specific wavelength: a fast rise in current is followed by a slow decrease in current.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we fabricated a gate-tuned photosensitive device based on aerosol-synthesized SWCNT and immobilized red FP. The device demonstrated a high photoresponse at the absorption bands of mKate2. The photoresponse is affected by the gate voltage, resulting in a change in the photocurrent sign due to the switching between dominating charge transfer mechanisms in SWCNT/PBASE/mKate2 conjugates. The switching is associated with the change between substrate-based photogating in deple-

tion mode and trapped charges from FP at interfaces with the nanotube in accumulation mode. The device provides features of optoelectronic memory with a volatile state lasting more than 5 min in accumulation mode. The presence of water molecules in the environment noticeably affects the negative photoresponse, supporting the mechanism of water tunnels as possible channels between the protein and SWCNT.

4. Experimental Section

Aerosol Synthesis of SWCNT: SWCNTs were produced by an aerosol CVD method. The method provides single-walled carbon nanotubes with tailored characteristics,^[40] and, most importantly, with a tailored bundle size: from individual nanotubes to thick rope-like agglomerates of tens of nm in thickness.^[41] Indeed, owing to the energy of lateral interaction between the nanotubes of ca. $950 \text{ eV } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$,^[42] it is almost impossible to obtain long nanotubes vital for electronic devices from a CNT powder. Carbon nanotubes were produced using the Boudouard reaction ($2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$) on the surface of Fe-based catalyst nanoparticles formed by means of thermal decomposition of ferrocene vapor. CO (99.99%, Linde Gas) flow was partially saturated with ferrocene vapor in a thermostated cartridge (28 °C) to reach a final concentration of 0.5 ppm at the reactor entrance. The length of nanotubes was controlled with the residence time, while the diameter distribution can be tuned by adding CO_2 .^[40] It should be noted that the residual catalyst nanoparticles remain on the nanotube and have a neglectable effect on the conductivity.^[43] For nanotube synthesis based on the Boudouard reaction, extensive TEM studies were performed to prove the practical absence of any multiwalled carbon nanotubes, which, in a certain sense, was similar to the exclusive formation of single-layer graphene via the similar Boudouard reaction.^[44] The main characteristics of SWCNTs were revealed through Raman and AFM measurements (Figures S2a,c and S6, Supporting Information).

FP Expression and Purification: mKate2 coding sequence was cloned into the pQE30 vector (Qiagen) with an N-terminal 6xHis tag. The E.coli cells of XL-1 Blue strain (Invitrogen) were used for the mKate2 expression. Cells were grown in conical flasks (100 mL of culture per 1 L flask) for 24 h at 37 °C in Excella E25 (New Brunswick Scientific) thermostated shaker at 220 rpm, followed by 24 h growth at room temperature and 140 rpm for protein maturation. Cell pellets were then lysed by ultrasound using a Sonic Dismembrator (Fisher Scientific) for 15 min total treatment time (35 cycles of 6 s sonication at 30% input power amplitude and 20 s in off-cycle, Sonics Vibra-Cell, tapered microtip 1/4”). Protein was purified using TALON metal-affinity resin (Clontech Laboratories, Takara Bio USA) according to the manufacturer’s protocol. The resin-immobilized protein was rinsed with 10 × volume of phosphate-buffered

saline (PBS, pH 7.4, GIBCO, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and washed with 10x volume of 10 mM imidazole in PBS. Further solubilization was performed with 250 mM imidazole pH 8 in PBS. Prior to the experiments, the protein solution was desalted by ultrafiltration with Amicon Ultra-0.5 10 K (Merck) filters (the final buffer was PBS pH 7.4) in a way to reach the final imidazole concentration far below 1 mM. The concentration of the resulting solution was adjusted to fit within the 3–5 mg mL⁻¹ range. The sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis analysis was performed on the mKate2 samples to confirm their homogeneity and purity.

An illustration of the mKate2 molecule was prepared based on the mKate spatial structure determined^[45] with the amino acid substitutions relevant to mKate2 introduced by mutagenesis in silico.

Device Fabrication: The SWCNTs were collected directly at the reactor outlet onto a 3-inch SiO₂ (200 nm)/Si(p⁺⁺) wafer. The collection time was selected to be 15 s to achieve the low density of individual nanotubes or bundles on the surface.^[7] The nanotubes were deposited as produced, without any additional purification. Optical photolithography was used to form a pattern of the 20/5 nm Pd/Cr pads to provide an electric contact to the nanotubes. Then the substrate was annealed in the vacuum at 600 °C to ensure the Ohmic contact of CNT with Pd. At the last stage, the connecting electrodes of 300/15 nm Au/Cr were formed. The wafer was scribed to 3 × 9 mm² chips and the chips with individual or small bundles of SWCNTs and non-zero current in depletion mode were selected for both control experiments and SWCNT/FP conjugate assembly.

Assembly of SWCNT/mKate2: Red FP mKate2 was immobilized on the surface of the SWCNT channel by means of amine-reactive crosslinking. Amino acids such as lysine (Lys) contain the amino group (-NH₂) that placed on the surface of mKate2 and enables chemical binding of FP.^[46] Owing to a high concentration of amino groups on the protein surface, a nonspecific orientation of the protein along the nanotube surface was likely to happen. For immobilization, a standard protocol was used for protein assembly with PBASE linker that binds to a nanotube through a π - π stacking interaction. 5 mM of PBASE solution in dimethyl formamide (DMF) was incubated for 5 hours.^[47] Then, the chip was washed consecutively in DMF, isopropanol, and distilled water for 2 min each, and dried. The 100 nM solution of mKate2 in 1 × PBS (pH 7.4) was deposited on the SWCNT/PBASE channel for 5 h in a dark place at 4 °C. The amino group of FP covalently reacts with the NHS esters of PBASE. After that, the samples were washed in PBS and distilled water for 2 min each to remove excess FPs and dried. Between measurements, the chip was kept in a dark place at normal conditions. The scheme of bionanohybrid assembly was presented in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).

Characterization: The properties of individual SWCNT were characterized using micro-Raman spectroscopy (Nano Scan Technology, Russia and Horiba XploRA Plus, France) with an excitation wavelength of 532 and 785 nm,^[48] power of 1 mW, and laser spot size of 0.5 μ m. Morphology was assessed by AFM (Solver-P47, NT-MDT, Russia) using silicon cantilevers with diamond tips Etalon HA_NC/FD/15 series (ScanSens, GmbH) in semi-contact mode with $f_{\text{RES}} = 140$ kHz. UV-vis spectra of glass substrate covered by SWCNT film were measured using a Cintra 4040 spectrophotometer (GBC Scientific Equipment, Australia). The electrical properties were measured using a semiconductor parameter analyzer IPPP 1/5 (MNIPI, Belarus). The electrical current was limited by 100 nA to ensure power consumption below 10 nW to avoid any thermal effects^[49] in the nanotube body. The optical response was investigated using a set of LEDs with wavelengths varying from 390 to 860 nm. LED was placed over the samples at a distance of ≈ 120 mm, resulting in the power density of the light flux of ≈ 30 mW cm⁻². All the measurements were performed under ambient conditions.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

D.K. and A.N. performed the nanotube synthesis, and A.K., N.N., and I.B. performed the device fabrication. A.B. performed the protein synthesis. A.K. and N.N. conducted the optical and electrical measurements. I.B. wrote the manuscript draft.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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field-effect transistors, fluorescent protein, long-term memory, photogating, single-walled carbon nanotubes

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